

The Nature and Composition of the Complexes of Mo(VI) with Halogen Substituted Ortho-Hydroxy Acetophenone Oxime

H. SINGH, U. K. RATHI* and N. SINGH**

Chemical Laboratories, D. S. College, Aligarh, Aligarh-202 001

Manuscript received 23 July 1979, accepted 29 December 1979

The complexes of molybdenum(VI) with 2-hydroxy-5-chloro and 2-hydroxy-5-bromo acetophenone oximes have been studied spectrophotometrically in water-ethanol medium. The yellow coloured solid complexes of above ligands were isolated by refluxing the metal and ligand solutions in stoichiometric ratio. These complexes were characterized by analytical, thermal, infra-red spectral and magnetic susceptibility data. The composition of above complexes comes out to be 1:2 (metal:ligand), the general formula being $\text{MoO}_3(\text{C}_8\text{H}_7\text{O}_2\text{NX})_2$; where X=Cl and Br. The IR spectral study of complexes show that these ligands act as bidentate ligand with molybdenum(VI) and coordination takes place by formation of M-O and M←N bonds through the oxygen of phenolic group and nitrogen of oxime group with metal. The magnetic susceptibility data reveals that complexes are diamagnetic, octahedral in nature and molecular weights determined by cryoscopic method show the monomer character. The stability constants are 5.5×10^8 and 2.31×10^8 ; and free energy of formation ΔF° are -12.11 and -11.59 K cal/mol in case of 2-hydroxy-5-chloro acetophenone oxime and 2-hydroxy-5-bromo acetophenone oxime respectively, determined spectrophotometrically applying the Mole-Ratio method.

THE reagents containing the system $\begin{array}{c} \text{OH} \\ | \\ \text{C}=\text{C}-\text{C}=\text{NOH} \\ | \quad | \quad | \end{array}$ are very good complexing agents. Therefore, salicylaldehyde¹⁻³, resacetophenone oxime⁴, ortho-hydroxy acetophenone oxime and its derivatives⁵⁻⁸ etc have been used. The present communication deals with the spectrophotometric, conductometric, thermal and spectral study of Mo(VI) complexes employing 2-hydroxy-5-chloro acetophenone oxime (HCAOX) and 2-hydroxy-5-bromo acetophenone oxime (HBAOX).

Experimental

Preparation of reagents: 2-Hydroxy-5-chloro acetophenone and 2-hydroxy-5-bromo acetophenone were prepared almost quantitatively by Fries migration⁹ of *p*-chlorophenyl acetate and *p*-bromophenyl acetate respectively. The corresponding oximes (HCAOX) and (HBAOX) prepared by usual methods were crystallised in ethanol, HBAOX (m.p.169°) and HCAOX (m.p.181°).

Ammonium molybdate solution: The standard solution⁹ of ammonium molybdate (J. T. Baker) was prepared by dissolving the salts in double distilled water. Ammonium acetate and acetic acid were used to maintain the pH.

A "spectronic-20" spectrophotometer was used for the measurement of optical density. The condu-

ctometric titrations were done with the help of Toshniwal conductometer and IR spectra was recorded on Perkin-Elmer spectrophotometer.

Spectrophotometric Study:

Absorption curve: Vosburgh and Coopers⁹ method was employed to determine the nature and number of complexes present. The formation of yellow coloured complexes take place in water-ethanol medium of Molybdenum(VI) with both ligands (HCAOX-HBAOX). The maximum absorption occurs at 385 nm only which suggests the formation of one complex with each ligand.

Effect of pH, time and addition of reagents: The yellow colour complex of Mo(VI) takes place in the pH range 2 to 5.5 but the maximum colour intensity was observed at pH 4.5 with both ligands. There is no change in colour intensity up to a week and sequence of reagent addition got no significant effect on optical density.

Composition of the complex: Jobs method of continuous variation¹⁰, mole ratio¹¹ and slope ratio¹² methods were employed to determine the stoichiometry (metal : ligand) of the complex. The results of these methods showed the 1 : 2 composition.

*To whom all correspondence should be made.

**Present address : Chemistry Department, Hindu College, Moradabad.

The stability constants of complexes in case of both ligands were determined by mole-ratio method using the following expression

$$K = \frac{1 - \alpha}{4.C^2. \alpha^3}$$

$$\text{where } \alpha = \frac{E_m - E_s}{E_m}$$

C is the concentration of complex and α is the degree of dissociation. The terms E_m and E_s having their usual meanings.

The stability constants obtained from above method are 5.5×10^8 and 2.31×10^8 , and the free energy of formation, calculated from the relation $\Delta F^\circ = RT \ln K$, are -12.11 and -11.59 K cal/mol for the complexes of both ligands (HCAOX) and (HBAOX) respectively.

Conductometric titrations :

The direct and indirect titrations and Jobs method by conductometry also reveal the same 1 : 2 (metal : ligand) stoichiometry of these complexes.

Isolation of solid complexes :

The stoichiometric mixtures of metal solution and ligand in water-ethanol 30 : 70 (v/v) was refluxed on water bath for six hours and cooled. A bright yellow coloured complex deposited in case of both ligands were washed with water and ethanol and then dried in vacuum. These complexes were crystallized in ethanol. The chemical analyses of these complexes is in conformity with the composition of mole ratio 1:2.

The elemental analyses showed the following results :

Complex	C%	H%	N%	Mo%	
$\text{MoO}_2(\text{C}_8\text{H}_7\text{O}_2\text{NCl})_2$	38.58	2.78	5.61	19.20	(Found)
	38.65	2.81	5.63	19.29	(Calcd.)
$\text{MoO}_2(\text{C}_8\text{H}_7\text{O}_2\text{NBr})_2$	33.80	2.38	4.80	16.62	(Found)
	32.76	2.56	4.77	16.37	(Calcd.)

Thermal analysis :

The molybdenum-HCAOX and molybdenum-HBAOX chelates are thermally stable up to 160°. This indicates that the complexes are not hydrated. TGA curves of the metal complexes showed a rapid loss in weight in which the ligands carbon residue is almost

completely lost is 200 to 500°. In the end, the residue of MoO_2 is left behind.

Spectral studies :

The infra-red spectra recorded in Nujol-Mul of ligands and complexes. The ligands show the strong absorption bands of phenolic groups but no such bands are obtained in complexes. The disappearance of this band clearly points out to the replacement of phenolic hydrogen by the metal. The C=N frequency is also lowered in the complex. The lowering in C=N frequency and replacement of phenolic hydrogen atom clearly indicates that chelation takes place through the oxygen of -OH group and nitrogen of =NOH group. Some main frequencies are tabulized here below :

Compound	OH (phenolic) cm^{-1}	-C=N cm^{-1}	-NO- cm^{-1}
$\text{C}_8\text{H}_8\text{O}_2\text{NCl}$	3300	1585	1280
$\text{MoO}_2(\text{C}_8\text{H}_7\text{O}_2\text{NCl})_2$	-	1570	1265
$\text{C}_8\text{H}_8\text{O}_2\text{NBr}$	3350	1590	1240
$\text{MoO}_2(\text{C}_8\text{H}_7\text{O}_2\text{NBr})_2$	-	1560	1230

Result and Discussion

The molar conductivity determined in dioxane shows the non-electrolytic behaviour of the complexes and the molecular weights determined by cryoscopic method reveal that these complexes are monomer in nature. The magnetic study of these complexes claims the octahedral diamagnetic character.

On the basis of above results, the structure of the complex can be depicted as :

(X = Cl and Br)

Acknowledgement

Author's have manyfold indebtedness to Dr. S. S. Gupta, Principal, D.S. College, Aligarh-202 001, for his moral support and UGC for financial assistance. One of the authors (U. K. Rathi) is grateful to Agra University, Agra for the award of UGC Junior Research Fellowship.

SINGH, RATHI & SINGH : THE NATURE AND COMPOSITION OF THE COMPLEXES OF MO(VI) ETC.

References

1. F. EPHRAIM, *Ber.*, 1930, 63B, 1928.
2. J. H. FLAGG and N. H. FURMAN, *Ind. Eng. Chem. Anal. Ed.*, 1940, 12, 529.
3. M. JEAN, *Bull. Soc. Chim.*, 1943, 10, 201.
4. K. S. BHATKI and M. B. KABADI, *J. Sci. Ind. Res.*, 1952, 11B, 346 ; *J. Univ. Bombay*, 1955, 24, 51.
5. S. N. PODDAR, *Z. Anal. Chem.*, 1957, 154, 254 ; 1957, 155, 327.
6. S. PRAKASH, Y. DUTT and R. P. SINGH, *Indian J. Chem.*, 1968, 6, 664.
7. A. I. VOGEL, "Quantitative Inorganic Analysis", Longmans Green & Co. Ltd., London, 2nd edition, 1960, p. 506.
8. K. FRIES, *Ber.*, 1908, 41, 427.
9. W. C. VOSBURGH and G. R. COOPER, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1942, 64, 1630.
10. P. JOB, *Annals. Chem.*, 1928, 9(10), 113.
11. YOE and JONES, *Ind. Eng. Chem. Anal. Edn.*, 1944, 16, 111.
12. HARVEY and MANNING, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1950, 72, 4488.